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The People You Can Count On in the Italian Regions in the Period 2013-2022

It decreased by 0.61% on average

Istat calculates the value of the people you can count on. The variable consists of the percentage of people aged 14 and over who have non-cohabiting relatives (in addition to parents, children, brothers, sisters, grandparents, grandchildren), friends or neighbors on whom they can count out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period 2013-2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of people to count on in 2022. Valle d'Aosta is in first place by value of people to count on, i.e. a value of 86.3 units, followed by the Marche with a value of 84.9, and from Sardinia with an amount of 84.7 units. In the middle of the table are Calabria with an amount of 82.6 units, followed by Umbria with an amount of 82.5 units and Abruzzo with an amount of 81.3 units. Sicily closes the ranking with an amount of 78.5 units, followed by Puglia with an amount of 77.8 units and Basilicata with an amount of 77 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change of people to count on between 2013 and 2022. Piedmont is in first place for value of the percentage change of people to count on with the value of 12.50% going from an amount of 73.60 units in 2013 up to a value of 82.80 units in 2022. Molise follows with a percentage variation equal to an amount of 8.13% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 75.00 units up to an amount of 81.10 units or equal to an absolute variation of 6.10 units. Umbria follows with a variation from an amount of 6.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 77.60 units up to a value of 82.50 units. In the middle of the table is Calabria with a variation equal to an amount of 2.61% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 80.50 units in 2013 up to an amount of 82.60 units in 2022. Followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to an amount of 1.83% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 82.00 units up to an amount of 83.50 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation from an amount of -0.12% equal to a variation from an amount of 82.70 units up to a value of 82.60 units. Piedmont closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of -5.05% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 85.20 units up to 80.90 units. Below is Trentino Alto Adige with a variation equal to an amount of -5.46% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 87.90 units in 2013 up to an amount of 83.10 units. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to an amount of -8.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 84.10 units in 2013 up to a variation of 77.00%. Between 2013 and 2022 the value of people to count on grew on average in the Italian regions by 0.61% from an amount of 81.22 units up to a value of 81.72 units.

The people to count on in the Italian macro-regions between 2013 and 2022. The value of the people to count on in the Italian macro-regions between 2013 and 2022 grew in the southern macro-regions, and decreased in the macro-regions central-northern. The value of people to count on grew by 5.34% in Southern Italy, by 4.00% in Southern Italy, by 1.52% in the Islands. The value of people to count on decreased by 1.21% in the North-East, by 1.70% in the Centre, by 1.93% in the North and by

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2.29% in the North-West. We can note that there is however a convergence between southern macro-regions and northern macro-regions around a value of people to count on of between 80-82%.

Clusterization with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Emilia Romagna, Sardinia, Tuscany, Veneto, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Dige, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Lombardy, Marche, Lazio, Basilicata, Molise, Abruzzo, Calabria;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Sicily, Campania.

Considering the average value of the clusters, it determines the following ordering of the clusters, namely: Cluster 1 > Cluster 2. Cluster 1 is made up of 17 regions belonging to various macro-regions and characterized by significant heterogeneity from a socio-economic point of view. Cluster 2 is instead made up of three southern regions, namely Puglia, Sicily and Campania. It therefore follows that the level of people to rely on in the central-northern regions tends to be high compared to some southern regions. This is a counterfactual consideration. In fact, it contrasts with the very widespread idea that southerners, especially those from Campania, Sicily and Puglia, are capable of having widespread social networks characterized by persistent social solidarity. On the contrary, the central-northern regions tend to have much higher values of people to count on, demonstrating not only a greater production but also a higher social capital.

Conclusions. The value of the people you can count on on average in the Italian regions had a fluctuating trend between 2013 and 2022. Between 2013 and 2015 the value of the people you can count on grew from an amount of 81.21 units up to a value of 83.07 units. It subsequently decreased to an amount of 81.4 units in 2017. Subsequently, between 2017 and 2019, the value of people to count on grew from an amount of 81.4 units to a value of 82.51 in 2020 and then decreased in 2021 to 80.98 and increased slightly in 2022 to 81.71 units. From a macro-regional point of view, there was a reduction in the value of people to count on in the centre-north and a growth in the southern regions between 2013 and 2022. However, we can note that on average 20% of the over-age population 14 has no people to rely on. That is, there are around 10 million Italians who have no people to rely on. A condition that most likely adds to conditions of poverty, unemployment, territorial inequality and which highlights the presence of a phenomenon of social discrimination that could reduce the efficiency of political and civil capital at a regional and national level.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Regione	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	85,2	81,4	81,8	84,1	81	82	82,1	79,7	80,7	80,9
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	84,1	84,9	88,4	84,6	88	86,3	87,9	85,4	86,9	86,3
Liguria	80,3	83,7	81,2	83	84,7	84,3	82,6	84,1	85,7	83,7
Lombardia	82,3	83,6	80,8	80,6	83,4	80,1	81,6	80,3	80,7	80,6

Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	87,9	88,1	89,9	87,8	88,6	87,7	86	87,5	82	83,1
Veneto	82	84,2	84,5	85	82,3	81,7	79,2	81,8	81,9	80,3
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	82	82,6	79,1	85,4	83	82,1	83,1	81,2	80,8	83,5
Emilia-Romagna	82,7	84	86,8	81,7	85,5	82,4	81,2	83	81,5	82,6
Toscana	83	85,1	86,8	85,4	81	83,4	82	82,7	80,5	79,9
Umbria	77,6	79,4	87,1	85,1	82,3	83,9	85,6	83,8	81,9	82,5
Marche	81	81,7	83,6	83,4	80	81	80,3	78,6	81,7	84,9
Lazio	83	83,3	78,5	80,9	78,7	82,6	79,7	82,8	81,6	80,2
Abruzzo	78,7	77,7	83,8	81,4	78,6	81,8	80,2	82,7	82,9	81,3
Molise	75	81,3	88,3	82,4	82,1	76,5	81,3	85,7	80,5	81,1
Campania	73,6	79,6	76	78,4	77,4	76,6	81	80,9	78,5	82,8
Puglia	78,1	74,5	77,3	75,4	71,5	77,8	83,4	77,2	78,4	77,8
Basilicata	84,1	80,1	81,2	82,2	83,3	83,7	84,3	86,5	72,8	77
Calabria	80,5	83,3	83,2	79	76,8	79,5	83,6	81,1	81	82,6
Sicilia	75,9	76,9	80,2	81,3	75,8	77,1	81,8	79,8	75,5	78,5
Sardegna	87,3	83	82,9	86,2	84	83,6	80,3	85,4	84,1	84,7

Macro-Regioni	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	82,9	83,6	82,9	82,8	83,5	81,7	81,5	81,5	81,4	81,3
Nord-ovest	82,9	83	81,1	81,9	82,9	81,1	81,8	80,5	81,2	81
Nord-est	82,8	84,3	85,3	84	84,2	82,5	81	82,7	81,6	81,8
Centro	82,3	83,4	82,4	82,9	79,9	82,7	80,9	82,3	81,3	80,9
Mezzogiorno	77,5	78,5	79,4	79,6	76,6	78,3	81,9	80,6	78,6	80,6
Sud	76,8	78,5	78,6	78,2	76,1	78,1	82,1	80,4	79	80,9
Isole	78,8	78,4	80,9	82,5	77,8	78,7	81,4	81,2	77,7	80